

North Carolina Division of Parks and Recreation
Department of Natural and Cultural Resources
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REFINING NC STATE PARK UNIT VISITATION ESTIMATES USING MOBILE TRACKING DATA

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INTRODUCTION

This report presents recommendations from previous research to integrate **Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE)** with additional data sources, such as **Mobile Tracking Data (MTD)** and trail counters, to generate more accurate visitation estimates.

To accomplish this, we collaborated with **PlayCore** and the location intelligence company **Placer.ai** to obtain MTD, which includes geolocation data from cellular phones. They provided monthly MTD for 41 state park units (40 state parks + Occoneechee Mountain SRA) throughout 2022. Additionally, we retrieved the monthly VPVM-VE for the same year using the NC Park Attendance Dashboard.

PLAYCORE

 Placer.ai

To evaluate the relationships between VPVM-VE and MTD, we conducted regression analysis for each of the 41 state park units. The results, presented in plots (see Appendix A. Panels A-E) and a comprehensive table detailing R-squared values, slopes, and intercepts, are discussed in this report. Parks with high R-squared values are candidates for adjustment factors that can be used to create Hybrid visitation estimates (HVE). Parks with low R-squared values are identified and recommendations are made to help better understand the discrepancy between the VPVM-VE and MTD datasets.

Figure 1 and Table 1 compare Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) and Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) for 2022, demonstrating consistently higher estimates via VPVM.

Figure 1. Overage of the Visitors per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) compared to Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) for each park by month in 2022.

Table 1. Results of analysis comparing aggregate 2022 Visitors per Vehicle Multiplier

Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) and the aggregate 2022 Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) for each NC state park. The VPVM-VE 2022 Overage represents the subtraction of the MTD from the VPVM-VE. The PVM-VE 2022 % Overage represents the VPVM-VE 2022 Overage divided by the VPVM-VE.

DIVISION UNIT NAME	PARK	REGION	VPVM-VE 2022 TOTAL	MTD 2022 TOTAL	VPVM-VE 2022 OVERAGE	VPVM-VE 2022 % OVERAGE
CAROLINA BEACH	CABE	COASTAL	856,418	242,190	614,228	71.72%
CARVERS CREEK	CACR	COASTAL	151,734	47,856	103,878	68.46%
CHIMNEY ROCK	CHRO	MOUNTAINS	371,276	466,953	-95,677	-25.77%
CLIFFS OF THE NEUSE	CLNE	COASTAL	200,931	125,315	75,616	37.63%
CROWDERS MOUNTAIN	CRMO	PIEDMONT	760,330	303,287	457,043	60.11%
DISMAL SWAMP	DISW	COASTAL	43,551	14,723	28,828	66.19%
ELK KNOB	ELKN	MOUNTAINS	46,005	25,789	20,216	43.94%
ENO RIVER	ENRI	PIEDMONT	843,439	212,603	630,836	74.79%
FALLS LAKE	FALA	PIEDMONT	1,244,806	596,032	648,774	52.12%
FORT FISHER	FOFI	COASTAL	1,108,980	333,126	775,854	69.96%
FORT MACON	FOMA	COASTAL	1,020,663	583,429	437,234	42.84%
GOOSE CREEK	GOCR	COASTAL	146,155	106,838	39,317	26.90%
GORGES	GORG	MOUNTAINS	180,052	91,421	88,631	49.23%
GRANDFATHER MOUNTAIN	GRMO	MOUNTAINS	96,035	109,654	-13,619	-14.18%
HAMMOCKS BEACH	HABE	COASTAL	210,236	98,485	111,751	53.16%
HAW RIVER	HARI	PIEDMONT	80,733	42,470	38,263	47.39%
HANGING ROCK	HARO	PIEDMONT	872,657	356,750	515,907	59.12%
JONES LAKE	JONE	PIEDMONT	148,719	74,047	74,672	50.21%
JORDAN LAKE	JORD	COASTAL	2,055,579	955,703	1,099,876	53.51%
JOCKEY'S RIDGE	JORI	COASTAL	982,328	405,757	576,571	58.69%
KERR LAKE	KELA	PIEDMONT	1,395,789	724,878	670,911	48.07%
LAKE JAMES	LAJA	MOUNTAINS	530,415	278,354	252,061	47.52%
LAKE NORMAN	LANO	PIEDMONT	881,370	229,764	651,606	73.93%
LAKE WACCAMAW	LAWA	COASTAL	185,333	138,453	46,880	25.30%
LUMBER RIVER	LURI	COASTAL	155,510	60,112	95,398	61.35%
MAYO RIVER	MARI	PIEDMONT	95,789	29,016	66,773	69.71%
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	MEMI	COASTAL	130,609	40,583	90,026	68.93%
MEDOC MOUNTAIN	MEMO	COASTAL	173,627	47,634	125,993	72.57%
MOUNT JEFFERSON	MOJE	MOUNTAINS	117,755	57,762	59,993	50.95%
MOUNT MITCHELL	MOMI	MOUNTAINS	332,691	155,308	177,383	53.32%
MORROW MOUNTAIN	MOMO	PIEDMONT	209,236	163,560	45,676	21.83%
NEW RIVER	NERI	MOUNTAINS	365,702	96,123	269,579	73.72%
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN	OCMO	PIEDMONT	172,716	48,472	124,244	71.94%
PETTIGREW	PETT	COASTAL	42,799	38,224	4,575	10.69%
PILOT MOUNTAIN	PIMO	PIEDMONT	1,052,678	231,290	821,388	78.03%
RAVEN ROCK	RARO	COASTAL	343,851	126,076	217,775	63.33%
SINGLETARY LAKE	SILA	COASTAL	25,360	12,926	12,434	49.03%
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	SOMO	MOUNTAINS	420,132	74,157	345,975	82.35%
STONE MOUNTAIN	STMO	MOUNTAINS	409,478	150,668	258,810	63.20%
WEYMOUTH WOODS SANDHILLS	WEWO	PIEDMONT	126,711	24,053	102,658	81.02%
WILLIAM B. UMSTEAD	WIUM	PIEDMONT	826,817	277,034	549,783	66.49%

2. REGRESSION ANALYSIS RESULTS: TABLES AND HISTOGRAMS

Table 2 presents the results of the analysis comparing VPVM-VE and MTD for each state park unit. The columns include Division Unit Name, Park, Region, R-squared values, slope values, and intercept values.

R-squared values show how much the MTD helps explain the differences (or variance) in the VPVM-VE. In simple terms, it tells us how well the mobile data matches the vehicle count data. If the R-squared value is high (close to 1), it means the mobile visit data does a great job of explaining how many vehicles are in the park. In other words, the number of mobile visits is closely linked to the number of vehicles, and mobile data helps predict vehicle counts very accurately. If the R-squared value is low (closer to 0), this means the mobile data doesn't explain much of the variation in the vehicle counts. This could mean there are other factors affecting the vehicle numbers that mobile data doesn't capture, like unique visitor behaviors at the park, weather patterns, or areas with poor mobile coverage. For parks with low R-squared values, it might indicate that mobile tracking data doesn't fully capture the visitation patterns at those parks, and further investigation is needed to understand what's causing the discrepancies.

Slope Values: Slope values show how strongly MTD and VPVM-VE are related. When the relationship between the two is strong (indicated by a high R-squared), the slope is useful for understanding the connection. If the slope is more than 1, it suggests that vehicle visits increase faster than mobile visits, while a slope less than 1 indicates that vehicle visits increase more slowly than mobile visits. However, if the R-squared value is low (the relationship is weak), the slope becomes less reliable, and its interpretation may not accurately reflect the data. In these cases, the slope should be interpreted with caution, as it may not accurately represent the relationship between the two datasets.

Intercept Values: Intercept values show the baseline number of vehicle visits when no mobile visits are recorded. A high intercept means that even when there are no mobile visits (i.e., MTD shows zero), many vehicle visits are still counted at the park. This suggests that some visitors may not be captured by the mobile tracking data, such as visitors who don't carry mobile devices or those who disable location tracking on their phones. On the other hand, a low or negative intercept suggests that either MTD is missing a significant portion of visitation or that vehicle visits are being overestimated by the VPVM-VE. In parks with high R-squared values, a high intercept indicates that while mobile data is capturing most visitation, there are still vehicle visits that mobile data misses. In parks with low R-squared values, this might indicate larger problems, like poor mobile coverage or incorrect vehicle counts.

For a more detailed interpretation of state park units' R-squared values, slope values, and intercept values, see Section 3: Interpretation of Results & Discussion.

Table 2. Results of analysis comparing Visitors per Vehicle Multiplier

Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) and Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) for each NC state park unit in the calendar year 2022. R-squared values, slope values, and intercept values depict the nature of the relationship between the two data types.

DIVISION UNIT NAME	PARK	REGION	R-SQUARED	SLOPE	INTERCEPT
CAROLINA BEACH	CABE	COASTAL	0.356175967	1.903509962	32.95057685
CARVERS CREEK	CACR	COASTAL	0.180358075	1.976318616	4.762941359
CHIMNEY ROCK	CHRO	MOUNTAINS	0.963429319	0.771201581	0.930092359
CLIFFS OF THE NEUSE	CLNE	COASTAL	0.291876654	0.874187919	7.615178416
CROWDERS MOUNTAIN	CRMO	PIEDMONT	0.970981882	2.017294904	12.37589005
DISMAL SWAMP	DISW	COASTAL	0.303158106	0.732309965	4.118119348
ELK KNOB	ELKN	MOUNTAINS	0.802748019	1.222975173	1.205474439
ENO RIVER	ENRI	PIEDMONT	0.619621341	1.932316384	36.05189498
FALLS LAKE	FALA	PIEDMONT	0.952996869	1.810468171	13.80908625
FORT FISHER	FOFI	COASTAL	0.93847867	2.308648738	28.32575672
FORT MACON	FOMA	COASTAL	0.900636442	1.12905223	30.16176556
GOOSE CREEK	GOCR	COASTAL	0.889054101	0.897343556	4.190384097
GORGES	GORG	MOUNTAINS	0.91229934	1.435055019	4.071486262
GRANDFATHER MOUNTAIN	GRMO	MOUNTAINS	0.929972426	0.786856639	0.812751839
HAMMOCKS BEACH	HABE	COASTAL	0.957566831	1.119022005	8.335759816
HAW RIVER	HARI	PIEDMONT	0.986636243	2.446579317	-0.013347613
HANGING ROCK	HARO	PIEDMONT	0.448692115	0.583369919	4.66310663
JONES LAKE	JONE	PIEDMONT	0.938498425	1.778881438	21.71120035
JORDAN LAKE	JORD	COASTAL	0.950325975	1.469189504	3.327493732
JOCKEY'S RIDGE	JORI	COASTAL	0.985873483	2.000247982	11.99466691
KERR LAKE	KELA	PIEDMONT	0.8851289	1.402982853	31.56646627
LAKE JAMES	LAJA	MOUNTAINS	0.982883453	1.142852652	17.69144941
LAKE NORMAN	LANO	PIEDMONT	0.916733318	2.022467394	34.72331682
LAKE WACCAMAW	LAWA	COASTAL	0.860974038	0.471981221	9.998815331
LUMBER RIVER	LURI	COASTAL	0.610200163	2.068296901	2.598378055
MAYO RIVER	MARI	PIEDMONT	0.023040069	0.719718659	6.242136949
MERCHANTS MILLPOND	MEMI	COASTAL	0.825581864	1.874074059	7.029779688
MEDOC MOUNTAIN	MEMO	COASTAL	0.466315884	1.194807857	6.843342728
MOUNT JEFFERSON	MOJE	MOUNTAINS	0.032438296	0.478293306	10.91719557
MOUNT MITCHELL	MOMI	MOUNTAINS	0.961718442	2.013339204	0.121708407
MORROW MOUNTAIN	MOMO	PIEDMONT	0.979754092	2.06862387	0.951430335
NEW RIVER	NERI	MOUNTAINS	0.951363306	4.011990736	-1.661882125
OCCONEECHEE MOUNTAIN	OCMO	PIEDMONT	0.73347395	1.64899496	7.732159693
PETTIGREW	PETT	COASTAL	0.806075419	0.463937937	2.088786359
PILOT MOUNTAIN	PIMO	PIEDMONT	0.967784724	3.932517103	11.9271766
RAVEN ROCK	RARO	COASTAL	0.920099254	2.355839007	3.903020113
SINGLETARY LAKE	SILA	COASTAL	0.654587453	0.364280517	1.720942503
SOUTH MOUNTAINS	SOMO	MOUNTAINS	0.554531513	4.709919373	5.904875752
STONE MOUNTAIN	STMO	MOUNTAINS	0.866579741	2.054311807	8.329912385
WEYMOUTH WOODS SANDHILLS	WEWO	PIEDMONT	0.85722248	1.244288316	8.065177761
WILLIAM B. UMSTEAD	WIUM	PIEDMONT	0.259500919	1.756186476	28.35780298

Two histograms, which are a special type of bar chart that shows how often something happens, illustrate the occurrences of R-squared values (Figure 2) and slope values (Figure 3) derived from the regression analysis. For example, each bar in the correlation figure shows how many parks fall into a certain range of correlation values. The taller the bar, the more parks have that level of correlation. If a bar is short, it means fewer parks have that value. These histograms help us understand how common or rare certain relationships are across parks in terms of their visitation data.

Figure 2. Correlation Histogram - VPVM-VE vs. MTD Monthly Visitation 2022.

This histogram displays the distribution of R-squared values derived from the regression analysis of VPVM-VE compared to MTD for state parks units in 2022. The blue bars represent the frequency of parks within specified R-squared value ranges, illustrating the strength of the correlation between the two datasets, with values ranging from 0 (indicating no correlation) to 1 (indicating perfect correlation). The orange cumulative probability curve shows the cumulative percentage of parks with R-squared values below or equal to each specific value along the x-axis. Notably, approximately 55% of parks have R-squared values below 0.9, indicating that many parks exhibit weak correlations between VPVM-VE and MTD.

Figure 3. Slope Histogram - VPVM-VE vs. MTD Monthly Visitation 2022.

This histogram displays the distribution of slope values derived from the regression analysis of VPVM-VE against mobile MTD for state park units in 2022. The blue bars indicate the frequency of parks within specified slope ranges, reflecting the relationship between MTD and VPVM-VE. The orange cumulative probability curve illustrates the cumulative percentage of parks that have slope values below or equal to each specific value along the x-axis, with slope values ranging from 0 to over 4. The majority of parks exhibit slopes between 1 and 2, indicating that vehicle count visitation estimates are typically one to two times greater than mobile data visitation estimates.

3. INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides a detailed examination of specific park results, analyzing the correlations between Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) and Mobile Tracking Data (MTD). Four parks have been selected to illustrate the variability in these relationships, highlighting the implications of both high and low R-squared values. The analysis focuses on three parks with high correlations (Chimney Rock State Park, New River State Park, and Lake Norman State Park) and one park with a very low correlation (Morrow Mountain State Park). These selections illustrate a range of slopes—from moderate to high—and highlight the differences in intercepts, providing insight into the effectiveness of MTD in estimating visitation levels.

3.1. Interpretation of Four Regression Results

Figure 4 shows the comparison of visitation estimates for Chimney Rock (CHRO).

The R-squared value for Chimney Rock State Park (CHRO) is 0.96, indicating that mobile visits account for 96% of the changes in vehicle visits. This reflects a strong relationship between the two datasets, suggesting that both are effectively capturing visitation patterns. The slope of the regression line is 0.77, meaning that for every 1,000 MTD visits, there are approximately 770 VPVM-VE visits. This indicates that the **VPVM-VE values are lower than expected based on the MTD**. This discrepancy could suggest that:

- MTD may not be capturing all visitors, possibly due to factors such as some visitors not carrying mobile devices or having location services turned off. Additionally, demographic differences may lead certain groups, such as older adults or families, to be less inclined to use mobile technology.
- Alternatively, VPVM-VE may not accurately reflect actual visitation levels, either because not all vehicles are accounted for in the vehicle counts or because the multiplier used to produce VPVM-VE from the raw vehicle count is inaccurate.

In either case, this discrepancy results in an **underestimation of VPVM-VE**. To address these issues, **Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVEs) should yield higher values than the VPVM-VE** for the same period, aligning them more closely with the values derived from the MTD. The intercept is 0.93, suggesting that even when mobile visits are zero, there are about 930 estimated vehicle visits. While still large, this is the fifth smallest intercept among the 27 parks with R-squared values above 0.8.

Figure 4. Chimney Rock State Park Regression Result.

This regression plot shows the relationship between VPVM-VE (in thousands) and MTD (in thousands) for Chimney Rock State Park in the Mountain region of North Carolina. The high R-squared value of 0.96 indicates a strong correlation between the two datasets. The moderate-low slope of 0.77 suggests that for every 1,000 mobile visits, there are approximately 770 vehicle visits, indicating that the VPVM-VE estimates are lower than expected based on MTD. The relatively low intercept of 0.93 means that even when no mobile visits are recorded, an estimated 930 vehicle visits still occur. The data points represent specific months in 2022, color-coded by month, with the symbol shape indicating season. The diagonal 1:1 line shows a perfect correlation between vehicle visits and mobile visits.

Figure 5 shows the comparison of visitation estimates for New River State Park (NERI).

The R-squared value for New River State Park (NERI) is 0.95, indicating that mobile visits account for 95% of the changes in vehicle visits. This reflects a strong relationship between the two datasets, suggesting that both are effectively capturing visitation patterns. The slope of the regression line is 4.01, the highest slope among the 27 highly correlated parks, meaning that for every 1,000 MTD visits, there are approximately 4,010 VPVM-VE visits. This indicates that the **VPVM-VE values are much higher** than expected based on the MTD. This discrepancy results in an **overestimation of VPVM-VE**. To address these issues, Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVEs) should yield **much lower values than the VPVM-VE** for the same time period, aligning them more closely with the values derived from the MTD.

The intercept for New River State Park is -1.66, suggesting that when there are no recorded mobile visits, the estimated baseline for vehicle visits is negative (-1.660). This suggests the VPVM-VE is not adequately capturing all the visitors as the MTD shows that visitors are present. Likely reasons for this, in light of the highly correlated data, include that:

- The Visitors Per Vehicle multiplier is set too high (indicating it should be lower) or
- The raw Vehicle Counts do not accurately capture all visitors.

This second option can be ruled out by checking the technology at the park currently. If it is all well-functioning, then this second reason should be considered.

In that case, given the strong correlation, the negative intercept (the lowest among the 27 parks with R-squared values above 0.8), and the highest slope among the parks (with only two highly correlated parks having slopes above 2.5), **it may be beneficial to build in a ~4 times reduction of the HVE** or reduce the VPV multiplier before using the Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) in the Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE). This adjustment would lower the VPVM-VE, effectively bringing the slope closer to 1, meaning for every additional MTD, there is an equivalent increase in VPVM-VE.

Figure 5. New River State Park Regression Result.

This regression plot shows the relationship between VPVM-VE (in thousands) and MTD (in thousands) for New River State Park in the Mountain region of North Carolina. The high R-squared value of 0.95 indicates a strong correlation between the two datasets. The highest slope of 4.01 suggests that for every 1,000 mobile visits, there are approximately 4,010 vehicle visits, indicating that the VPVM-VE estimates are significantly higher than expected based on MTD. The negative intercept of -1.66 means that even when no mobile visits are recorded, the estimated baseline for vehicle visits is negative, suggesting the VPVM-VE does not fully capture all visitors as indicated by MTD. The data points represent specific months in 2022, color-coded by month, with the symbol shape indicating season. The diagonal 1:1 line shows a perfect correlation between vehicle visits and mobile visits.

Figure 6 shows the comparison of visitation estimates for Lake Norman State Park (LANO).

The R-squared value for Lake Norman State Park (LANO) is 0.92, indicating that mobile visits account for 92% of the changes in vehicle visits, reflecting a strong relationship between the two datasets. The slope of the regression line is 2.02, which ranks as the 8th highest among the 27 highly correlated parks, meaning that for every 1,000 MTD visits, there are approximately 2,020 VPVM-VE visits. This suggests that the VPVM-VE values are higher than expected based on the MTD. This suggests an overestimation of VPVM-VE, albeit by half as much as seen at New River State Park.

To address these issues, Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVEs) should yield lower values than the VPVM-VE for the same period, aligning them more closely with the values derived from the MTD. To clarify, this overestimation is not an absolute judgment on the accuracy of either dataset. Instead, it reflects the fact that VPVM-VE tends to overestimate visitation relative to MTD for this specific park. The high slope suggests that VPVM-VE is disproportionately higher than MTD, but this doesn't mean that MTD is necessarily more accurate. It simply indicates that adjustments to the VPVM-VE are needed for a more balanced visitation estimate.

A significant difference in this result, when compared to the previous case at New River State Park, is the intercept, which is the highest among the highly correlated parks. This positive intercept indicates a baseline visitation level that remains substantial even when mobile visits are recorded as zero. Unlike New River, where the negative intercept suggested potential issues with capturing all visitors, Lake Norman's positive intercept suggests that MTD may not fully capture all visitors. This could be due to some visitors not carrying mobile devices or having location services turned off, along with demographic differences that make certain groups, such as older adults or families, less inclined to use mobile technology.

Despite the discrepancies, the high correlation and moderately high slope affirm the reliability of the relationship between the datasets. Understanding the root causes of the higher VPVM-VE baseline and high slope could lead to more effective Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVEs). To address these issues, it may be beneficial to apply a ~2 times reduction in the HVE or to adjust the Visitors Per Vehicle (VPV) multiplier before using the VPVM-VE in the HVEs, as suggested for New River State Park.

Figure 6. Lake Norman State Park Regression Result.

This regression plot shows the relationship between VPVM-VE (in thousands) and MTD (in thousands) for Lake Norman State Park in the Piedmont region of North Carolina. The high R-squared value of 0.92 indicates a strong correlation between the two datasets. The moderately high slope of 2.02 suggests that for every 1,000 mobile visits, there are approximately 2,020 vehicle visits, indicating that the VPVM-VE estimates are higher than expected based on MTD, but less so than at New River State Park (Figure 5). The highest intercept of 34.72 means that even when no mobile visits are recorded, the estimated baseline for vehicle visits is 34,720, suggesting that VPVM-VE may be overestimating visitation at times when mobile data is missing or underreported. The data points represent specific months in 2022, color-coded by month, with the symbol shape indicating season. The diagonal 1:1 line shows a perfect correlation between vehicle visits and mobile visits.

Figure 7 shows the comparison of visitation estimates for Morrow Mountain State Park (MOMO).

The R-squared value for Morrow Mountain State Park (MOMO) is only 0.03, indicating that just 3% of the variance in vehicle visits can be explained by mobile visits. This extremely low correlation suggests that either:

- MTD fails to effectively capture the visitation patterns, or
- The raw Vehicle Counts do not accurately capture all visitors.
- Both datasets may not adequately capture the true visitation patterns.

The low R-squared value raises significant concerns about the reliability of both datasets, as they do not align to provide an accurate picture of park visitation. Given this weak relationship, the slope and intercept from the regression analysis are not meaningful indicators of visitation and should not be used in an HVE. Determining the reasons behind this discrepancy will be essential for improving the accuracy of visitation estimates at Morrow Mountain State Park.

Figure 7. Morrow Mountain State Park Regression Result.

This regression plot shows the relationship between VPVM-VE (in thousands) and MTD (in thousands) for Morrow Mountain State Park in the Piedmont region of North Carolina. The very low R-squared value of 0.03 indicates a very weak correlation between the two datasets, meaning that mobile visits (MTD) do not explain the variation in vehicle visits (VPVM-VE) at this park. This suggests that either the mobile data is not accurately capturing visitation at this park, or the vehicle counts do not reflect actual visitor behavior. The slope and intercept values are less meaningful in this case due to the weak correlation. Notably, data from December through May lie above the slope line, suggesting that during these months, vehicle visits are higher than what the mobile data predicts. In contrast, data from June through November fall below the slope line, indicating that vehicle visits are lower than what MTD estimates would suggest for those months. The data points represent specific months in 2022, color-coded by month, with the symbol shape indicating season. The diagonal 1:1 line shows a perfect correlation between vehicle visits and mobile visits.

3.2. Parks with Low R-squared Values

Here is a list of parks that have R-squared values less than 0.8. For these parks, 2022 MTD offers a relatively poor reflection of vehicle count visitation estimates:

Piedmont Region

- Occoneechee Mountain State Natural Area (OCMO): R-squared = 0.733
- Eno River State Park (ENRI): R-squared = 0.620
- Haw River State Park (HARI): R-squared = 0.449
- William B. Umstead State Park (WIUM): R-squared = 0.260
- Morrow Mountain State Park (MOMO): R-squared = 0.032
- Mayo River State Park (MARI) : R-squared = 0.023

Coastal Region

- Singletary Lake State Park (SILA): R-squared = 0.655
- Lumber River State Park (LURI): R-squared = 0.610
- Merchants Millpond State Park (MEMI): R-squared = 0.466
- Carolina Beach State Park (CABE): R-squared = 0.356
- Dismal Swamp State Park (DISW): R-squared = 0.303
- Cliffs of the Neuse State Park (CLNE): R-squared = 0.292
- Carvers Creek State Park (CACR): R-squared = 0.180

Mountains Region

- South Mountains State Park (SOMO): R-squared = 0.555

Low R-squared values indicate that mobile tracking data explains less than half of the variance in vehicle count estimates (VPVM-VE) for these parks. In simpler terms, this means that the mobile tracking data does not account for a significant portion of the differences in vehicle counts observed at these parks. For instance, if the R-squared value is 0.3, it suggests that only 30% of the changes in vehicle counts can be explained by the mobile tracking data, leaving 70% of the variance unexplained by this data source.

This finding underscores the limitations of relying solely on mobile tracking data for accurate visitation estimates across the park system, as it may not fully capture visitor patterns influenced by various factors. Specifically, the low R-squared values suggest that mobile tracking data does not account for factors affecting vehicle counts, such as incomplete vehicle count capture due to unrecorded entrances and multipliers that may not reflect actual visitation patterns, particularly in parks with unique visitor demographics. Additionally, limitations in mobile tracking data itself—such as some visitors not carrying devices, demographic factors that reduce mobile technology usage, and untracked short visits—further contribute to the discrepancy between mobile visits and vehicle counts. Thus, both data sources have limitations that affect their ability to explain variance in visitation estimates.

3.3. Parks with High R-squared Values

For the parks with R-squared values above 0.8, the intercepts range from -1.66 to 34.72, with a median of 8.07 and an average of 10.22. In analyzing these intercepts, it is important to note that they typically represent a single intercept from a regression model that combines both Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) and Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE). This single intercept signifies the expected visitation levels when both datasets indicate zero visits, providing a baseline for understanding visitation patterns.

Here are a few reasons why intercepts may be high in the context of comparing MTD and VPVM-VE:

- 1. VPVM-VE Multipliers:** The multipliers applied to vehicle counts in the VPVM-VE can inflate the baseline visitation numbers. These multipliers are intended to estimate total visitation based on assumed vehicle occupancy, while the MTD has no multiplier applied to adjust the number of phones captured to an estimation of visitation.
- 2. Regular Visitors Without Phones:** Certain parks may attract a dedicated visitor base that regularly returns but does not use mobile devices. This behavior can result in a higher baseline visitation level reflected in the intercept, as these visitors are not captured in the MTD.
- 3. Limited Cell Phone Coverage:** In some areas, poor or nonexistent cell phone coverage may prevent accurate tracking of mobile visits. This can lead to an underrepresentation of actual visitation in the MTD, contributing to a higher intercept when compared to VPVM-VE.
- 4. Counts of Non-Visitor Vehicles:** VPVM-VE may include counts of vehicles that are not necessarily associated with park visitors, such as maintenance or delivery vehicles. This inclusion can artificially elevate the baseline visitation estimate.

These factors highlight the complexities involved in accurately estimating park visitation and underscore the importance of understanding the underlying data sources and methodologies.

4. UTILIZING STRONG VISITORS PER VEHICLE MULTIPLIER ESTIMATES (VPVM-VE) AND MOBILE TRACKING DATA (MTD) CORRELATIONS TO REFINE VISITATION ESTIMATES

For parks that are highly correlated, even if the slope suggests VPVM-VE underestimates or overestimates actual visitation or intercept implies that there is always a significant VPVM-VE, even if the MTD shows zero activity, the observed relationship can potentially be utilized to refine visitation estimates through the creation of Adjustment Factors (AFs) and Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE).

4.1. Three Ways to Utilize the Observed Relationship

The approach for calculating AFs and HVEs should depend on the context of the data and the availability of MTD.

Option 1

When no additional mobile data is acquired, this formula takes VPVM-VE and creates a HVE:

$$\text{HVE} = (\text{VPVM-VE} \times \text{Adjustment Factor}) + \text{Intercept}$$

This approach leverages future VPVM-VE to generate HVE, allowing the model to account for the relationship between vehicle counts and mobile visits. The intercept provides a baseline visitation level that may not be captured by vehicle counts alone.

Option 2

If MTD is regularly acquired and it is a reliable indicator of visitation at this park, a preferred formula may be:

$$\text{HVE} = (\text{MTD} \times \text{Adjustment Factor}) + \text{Intercept}$$

This method adjusts raw MTD to produce visitation estimates. The adjustment factor modifies MTD to reflect expected visitation levels, while the intercept accounts for baseline visitation that may exist even when mobile visits are low or absent.

Option 3

Employing both datasets could prove useful. However, to utilize this formula for future estimates, one would need to regularly obtain MTD or assume similar visitation patterns from year to year, consistently applying the 2022 MTD figures in the equation:

$$\text{HVE} = (\text{MTD} \times w1) + (\text{VPVM-VE} \times w2) + \text{Intercept}$$

This approach allows for a weighted combination of both datasets, ensuring a robust visitation estimate that reflects the strengths of each data source. By applying different weights to MTD and VPVM-VE, this formula adapts to varying levels of data reliability and correlation between the two sources. The inclusion of the intercept enhances the accuracy of HVE by accounting for baseline visitation levels, making this formula a flexible option for parks with consistent mobile tracking data and varying visitation patterns.

4.2. Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) and Adjustment Factor

Because Option 1 from the previous section uses the least resources as it requires no additional mobile data, this report will cover creating HVE based solely on future VPVM-VE using the regression equations coefficient in the calculation:

$$\text{HVE} = (\text{VPVM-VE} \times \text{Adjustment Factor}) + \text{Intercept}$$

This section outlines the development of an adjustment factor to improve the accuracy of the Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) by incorporating insights from Mobile Tracking Data (MTD). By leveraging the observed relationships between VPVM-VE and MTD, we can create park-specific adjustment factors that refine visitation estimates previously based solely on vehicle counts. This approach aims to provide a more accurate representation of actual visitor behavior within each park.

Parks exhibiting an R-squared value above 0.8 are good candidates for adjustment and the creation of a Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE), given the strong correlations observed. For each highly correlated park, we can tailor the adjustment factor based on the slope of the regression to enhance the accuracy of visitation estimates.

We propose the following formula for the Adjustment Factor:

$$\text{Adjustment Factor} = 1 - ((\text{slope} - k) / 10)$$

Where k is a reference value that varies depending on the slope:

- For slopes between 0.75 and 1.25, $k = 1$
- For slopes above 1.25, $k = 0.95$
- For slopes below 0.75, $k = 1.05$

The distance between the slope and k informs the magnitude of the adjustment. The further the slope is from k , the more significant the adjustment, allowing the formula to flexibly respond to the specific visitation dynamics of each park.

A slope of 1 indicates that for every additional mobile visit, there is an equivalent increase in vehicle visits, suggesting that mobile data accurately captures visitation patterns and no adjustment is needed. By using $k = 1$, we reinforce this reliability, ensuring the adjustment factor does not significantly alter the visitation estimate.

When slopes fall below 1, it means that for each additional mobile visit recorded, there are fewer vehicle visits than expected based on vehicle count estimates. This suggests that the mobile tracking data (MTD) isn't capturing all the visitors at the park for several reasons. Many people might not have mobile devices with them or may have their location services turned off, leading to uncounted visits. Others might avoid using mobile apps due to privacy concerns or simply because they find them hard to use. Additionally, certain parks might attract visitors who are less likely to use technology, like older adults or families. Quick visits, such as stopping for a rest or a picnic, might also be missed by mobile tracking, leading to significant gaps between vehicle counts and mobile visits. Furthermore, the way vehicle counts are estimated may not consider all the people traveling in each vehicle, which could further confuse the comparison between the two data sources.

In these cases, we should increase the Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE) to better match the higher visitor numbers indicated by vehicle counts. This adjustment effectively pushes the slope of the regression line closer to an idealized 1-to-1 relationship, thereby increasing the HVE relative to the VPVM-VE.

On the other hand, when the slope is above 1, it indicates that each additional mobile visit corresponds to a greater number of vehicle visits, meaning that the number of vehicle visits increases at a faster rate than the number of mobile visits. This indicates that mobile tracking may not fully capture the total number of visitors for similar reasons, such as differences in who visits the park and how often they use technology. In this situation, the adjustment factor is used to lower the HVE, acknowledging that vehicle counts might reflect a higher level of visitation than what mobile data shows. By doing so, the HVE effectively pushes the slope of the regression line towards the idealized 1-to-1 relationship, decreasing the HVE relative to the VPVM-VE. For example, if we set $k = 0.95$, the adjustment accounts for the disparity between the two datasets, ensuring that the HVE is calibrated to more accurately reflect actual park usage without inflating the visitor numbers beyond what the vehicle counts indicate.

Using this formula, the Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE) can be derived for each park meeting the R-squared and slope criteria:

$$\text{HVE} = \text{VPVM-VE} \times \text{Adjustment Factor} + \text{Intercept}$$

This formula applies the observed relationships in each park to adjust visitation estimates, ensuring they are better aligned with actual visitor patterns as indicated by both data sources.

4.3. Table of Proposed Adjustment Factors

Table 3 presents parks that meet the criteria of having an R-squared value greater than 0.8. The table includes each park, its Region, R-squared value, Slope, and Intercept, along with their respective k values and calculated Adjustment Factors (AF). The final two columns on the right are the original VPVM-VE and MTD for 2022. Many of these fields will be used as input for HVE calculations in the following tables in Section 5.

Table 3. Visitation adjustment factors for NC State Park units with R-squared values > 0.8 for comparisons of Visitors per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) and Mobile Tracking Data (MTD).

PARK	REGION	R-SQUARED	SLOPE	INTERCEPT	K	ADJUSTMENT FACTOR (AF)	VPVM-VE (JAN 2022)	MTD (JAN 2022)
NERI	MOUNTAINS	0.951	4.01	-1.66	0.95	0.69	6,664	3,121
PIMO	PIEDMONT	0.968	3.93	11.93	0.95	0.70	51,015	8,430
HARO	PIEDMONT	0.987	2.45	-0.01	0.95	0.85	23,461	8,961
RARO	COASTAL	0.920	2.36	3.90	0.95	0.86	16,553	6,353
FOFI	COASTAL	0.938	2.31	28.33	0.95	0.86	26,896	3,510
MOMI	MOUNTAINS	0.980	2.07	0.95	0.95	0.89	2,938	1,084
STMO	MOUNTAINS	0.867	2.05	8.33	0.95	0.89	13,652	2,349
LANO	PIEDMONT	0.917	2.02	34.72	0.95	0.89	44,371	4,809
CRMO	PIEDMONT	0.971	2.02	12.38	0.95	0.89	43,088	14,439
MOJE	MOUNTAINS	0.962	2.01	0.12	0.95	0.89	2,386	1,841
JORD	PIEDMONT	0.986	2.00	11.99	0.95	0.89	22,915	12,069
MEMO	COASTAL	0.826	1.87	7.03	0.95	0.91	11,556	1,444
FALA	PIEDMONT	0.953	1.81	13.81	0.95	0.91	18,432	7,325
JORI	COASTAL	0.938	1.78	21.71	0.95	0.92	24,104	4,051
JONE	COASTAL	0.950	1.47	13.33	0.95	0.95	6,006	2,220
GORG	MOUNTAINS	0.912	1.44	4.07	0.95	0.95	5,230	2,095
KELA	PIEDMONT	0.885	1.40	31.57	0.95	0.95	21,788	5,527
WEWO	PIEDMONT	0.857	1.24	8.07	1	0.98	10,058	1,619
ELKN	MOUNTAINS	0.803	1.22	1.21	1	0.98	2,712	1,312
LAJA	MOUNTAINS	0.983	1.14	17.69	1	0.99	22,706	4,235
FOMA	COASTAL	0.901	1.13	30.16	1	0.99	44,793	12,530
HABE	COASTAL	0.958	1.12	8.34	1	0.99	9,900	2,300
GOCR	COASTAL	0.889	0.90	4.19	1	1.01	4,852	2,839
GRMO	MOUNTAINS	0.930	0.79	0.81	1	1.02	2,120	3,012
CHRO	MOUNTAINS	0.963	0.77	0.93	1	1.02	12,121	13,228
LAWA	COASTAL	0.861	0.47	10.00	1.05	1.06	10,149	2,427
PETT	COASTAL	0.806	0.46	2.09	1.05	1.06	2,647	838

4.4. Table of Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) with and without Inclusion of the Intercepts

Given the discussion of reasons why intercepts may be high in Section 4.3, it is important to examine how the intercept influences the increase and percent increase for each park. In Table 4 below, the green field has the parks Intercept, AF, Slope, and VPVM-VE estimates for January 2022. The Orange model presents the Hybrid Visitation Model 1 (HVE1) which does not utilize the intercept. The Purple model presents the Hybrid Visitation Model 1 (HVE1) which does utilize the intercept. For each model, there is an HVE estimate using January 2022 data and the formula **HVE = VPVM-VE × Adjustment Factor**, both with and without the intercept. Then, the difference between the HVEs and VPVM-VE, as well as the percentage increase of the HVEs from the VPVM-VE, are provided in the table below.

For HVE1, the HVE1 % Increase (Jan 2022) ranged from -31% to 2%, while the HVE2 % Increase (Jan 2022) ranged from -15% to 140%. For most parks, the percent increase of the HVE is higher (and in many cases much higher) for HVE2 (with the intercept) compared to HV1(without the intercept), with exceptions for only HARO and NERI, which have negative intercepts. Given the observed influence of the intercept in the HVE2 % Increase and the reasons discussed in section 4.3 for why intercepts may be high in the context of comparing MTD and VPVM-VE, a desired estimate may land somewhere between these two models.

Table 4. Comparison of Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) with and without the Inclusion of the Intercept for NC State Park Units (January 2022). This table compares two Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE) models calculated for North Carolina state park units in January 2022, with and without the inclusion of the intercept from the regression results. The table provides key data for each state park unit (highlighted in green), including the intercept, adjustment factor (AF), slope, and VPVM-VE data used in the regression analysis. It then presents two HVE models: (in orange) HVE1, which excludes the intercept, and (in purple) HVE2, which includes the intercept. The table also shows the difference and percentage increase for both HVE1 and HVE2 in comparison to the VPVM-VE, offering insights into how the inclusion of the intercept impacts the refinement of visitation estimates across various state park units.

Table 4. Comparison of Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) with and without the Inclusion of the Intercept for NC State Park Units (January 2022).

This table compares two Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE) models calculated for North Carolina state park units in January 2022, with and without the inclusion of the intercept from the regression results. The table provides key data for each state park unit (highlighted in green), including the intercept, adjustment factor (AF), slope, and VPVM-VE data used in the regression analysis. It then presents two HVE models: (in orange) HVE1, which excludes the intercept, and (in purple) HVE2, which includes the intercept. The table also shows the difference and percentage increase for both HVE1 and HVE2 in comparison to the VPVM-VE, offering insights into how the inclusion of the intercept impacts the refinement of visitation estimates across various state park units.

PARK	INTERCEPT	AF	SLOPE	VPVM-VE (JAN 2022)	HVE1 = [VPVM-VE (JAN 2022) *AF]	HVE1 (JAN 2022) INCREASE	HVE1 % INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE2 = [VPVM-VE (JAN 2022) *AF] + INTERCEPT	HVE2 (JAN 2022) INCREASE	HVE2 % INCREASE (JAN 2022)
NERI	-1.66	0.69	4.01	6,664	4,623	-2,041	-31%	2,962	-3,702	56%
PIMO	11.93	0.70	3.93	51,015	35,800	-15,215	-30%	47,727	-3,288	-6%
HARO	-0.01	0.85	2.45	23,461	19,950	-3,511	-15%	19,937	-3,524	-15%
RARO	3.90	0.86	2.36	16,553	14,226	-2,327	-14%	18,129	1,576	10%
FOFI	28.33	0.86	2.31	26,896	23,242	-3,654	-14%	51,568	24,672	92%
MOMI	0.95	0.89	2.07	2,938	2,609	-329	-11%	3,561	623	21%
STMO	8.33	0.89	2.05	13,652	12,144	-1,508	-11%	20,474	6,822	50%
LANO	34.72	0.89	2.02	44,371	39,612	-4,759	-11%	74,336	29,965	68%
CRMO	12.38	0.89	2.02	43,088	38,489	-4,599	-11%	50,865	7,777	18%
MOJE	10.12	0.89	2.01	2,386	2,132	-254	-11%	2,254	-132	-6%
JORD	11.99	0.89	2.00	22,915	20,508	-2,407	-11%	32,503	9,588	42%
MEMO	17.03	0.91	1.87	11,556	10,488	-1,068	-9%	17,518	5,962	52%
FALA	13.81	0.91	1.81	18,432	16,846	-1,586	-9%	30,655	12,223	66%
JORI	21.71	0.92	1.78	24,104	22,106	-1,998	-8%	43,817	19,713	82%
JONE	13.33	0.95	1.47	6,006	5,694	-312	-5%	9,022	3,016	50%
GORG	4.07	0.95	1.44	5,230	4,976	-254	-5%	9,048	3,818	73%
KELA	31.57	0.95	1.40	21,788	20,801	-987	-5%	52,368	30,580	140%
WEWO	8.07	0.98	1.24	10,058	9,812	-246	-2%	17,877	7,819	78%
ELKN	1.21	0.98	1.22	2,712	2,652	-60	-2%	3,857	1,145	42%
LAJA	17.69	0.99	1.14	22,706	22,382	-324	-1%	40,073	17,367	76%
FOMA	30.16	0.99	1.13	44,793	44,215	-578	-1%	74,377	29,584	66%
HABE	8.34	0.99	1.12	9,900	9,782	-118	-1%	18,118	8,218	83%
GOGR	4.19	1.01	0.90	4,852	4,902	50	1%	9,092	4,240	87%
GRMO	0.81	1.02	0.79	2,120	2,165	45	2%	2,978	1,858	40%
CHRO	0.93	1.02	0.77	12,121	12,398	277	2%	13,328	1,207	10%
LAWA	10.00	1.06	0.47	10,149	10,736	587	6%	20,734	10,585	104%
PETT	2.09	1.06	0.46	2,647	2,802	155	6%	4,891	2,244	85%

4.5. A Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) that splits the percent increase between HVEs with and without the Intercept

Given the observed influence of the intercept on Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) and the potential for these intercepts to be inflated, a promising solution lies in scaling the intercept to achieve a balance between the two models. Adjusting the intercept can help align the raw data from Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) with the more established visitation estimates from VPVM-VE, thereby refining our overall visitation estimates.

A high intercept in the regression model indicates a substantial baseline visitation level, suggesting that even when mobile visits are recorded as zero, there is still a significant estimated number of vehicle visits. This suggests that the baseline visitation estimates may be inflated compared to the actual visitor activity captured by Mobile Tracking Data (MTD). Consequently, adjustments may be necessary to ensure that the visitation estimates more accurately reflect true visitor patterns.

One option for scaling is to split the difference between the percentage increase for the Model not including the intercept HVE1 and the model that includes the intercept HVE2.

$$\text{HVE3 \% Increase} = \text{HVE2 \% Increase} - (\text{HVE2 \% Increase} - \text{HVE1 \% Increase})/2$$

Then the increase HVE3 estimate compared to VPVM-VE can be calculated:

$$\text{HVE3_Increase} = \text{VPVM-VE_jan} * \text{HVE3 \% Increase}$$

And, finally, the HVE3 estimate can be calculated by adding the Increase (which can be negative) to the VPVM-VE:

$$\text{HVE3} = \text{VPVM-VE_jan} + \text{HVE3_Increase}$$

In Table 5 below to the far right and with no background color, the HVE3 results are presented along with each park's VPVM-VE, and the HVE1 and HVE2 Model attributes.

Table 5. Comparison of Hybrid Visitation Estimates (HVE) Models for NC State Park Units (January 2022): HVE1 and HVE2 (with and without Intercept), and HVE3 (with Additional Adjustments).

This table presents three Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE) models for North Carolina state park units in January 2022. The key data for each state park unit (highlighted in green) includes the park name and the VPVM-VE data used in the regression analysis. The table compares the following models: (in orange) HVE1, which excludes the intercept; (in purple) HVE2, which includes the intercept; and (in white) HVE3, which incorporates additional adjustments based on the observed relationships, using the percent increase from both HVE1 and HVE2. The new white fields for HVE3 apply the formula from Section 4.4 to refine the visitation estimates further. The table also displays the difference and percentage increase for HVE1, HVE2, and HVE3 when compared to the VPVM-VE, providing insights into how the inclusion of the intercept and additional adjustments impact the visitation estimates across various state park units.

PARK	VPVM -VE (JAN 2022)	HVE1 = [VPVM-VE (JAN 2022) *AF]	HVE1 INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE1 % INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE2 = [VPVM-VE (JAN 2022) * AF] + INTERCEPT	HVE2 INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE2 % INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE3 % INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE3 INCREASE (JAN 2022)	HVE3= VPVM-VE (JAN 2022) + HVE3 INCREASE
NERI	6,664	4,623	-2,041	-30.6%	2,962	-3,702	-55.6%	-43.1%	-2871	3793
PIMO	51,015	35,800	-15,215	-29.8%	47,727	-3,288	-6.4%	-18.1%	-9252	41763
HARO	23,461	19,950	-3,511	-15.0%	19,937	-3,524	-15.0%	-15.0%	-3518	19943
RARO	16,553	14,226	-2,327	-14.1%	18,129	1,576	9.5%	-2.3%	-376	16177
FOFI	26,896	23,242	-3,654	-13.6%	51,568	24,672	91.7%	39.1%	10509	37405
MOMI	2,938	2,609	-329	-11.2%	3,561	623	21.2%	5.0%	147	3085
STMO	13,652	12,144	-1,508	-11.0%	20,474	6,822	50.0%	19.5%	2657	16309
LANO	44,371	39,612	-4,759	-10.7%	74,336	29,965	67.5%	28.4%	12603	56974
CRMO	43,088	38,489	-4,599	-10.7%	50,865	7,777	18.0%	3.7%	1589	44677
MOJE	2,386	2,132	-254	-10.6%	2,254	-132	-5.5%	-8.1%	-193	2193
JORD	22,915	20,508	-2,407	-10.5%	32,503	9,588	41.8%	15.7%	3591	26506
MEMO	11,556	10,488	-1,068	-9.2%	17,518	5,962	51.6%	21.2%	2447	14003
FALA	18,432	16,846	-1,586	-8.6%	30,655	12,223	66.3%	28.9%	5319	23751
JORI	24,104	22,106	-1,998	-8.3%	43,817	19,713	81.8%	36.7%	8858	32962
JONE	6,006	5,694	-312	-5.2%	9,022	3,016	50.2%	22.5%	1352	7358
GORG	5,230	4,976	-254	-4.9%	9,048	3,818	73.0%	34.1%	1782	7012
KELA	21,788	20,801	-987	-4.5%	52,368	30,580	140.4%	67.9%	14796	36584
WEWO	10,058	9,812	-246	-2.4%	17,877	7,819	77.7%	37.7%	3787	13845
ELKN	2,712	2,652	-60	-2.2%	3,857	1,145	42.2%	20.0%	542	3254
LAJA	22,706	22,382	-324	-1.4%	40,073	17,367	76.5%	37.5%	8521	31227
FOMA	44,793	44,215	-578	-1.3%	74,377	29,584	66.0%	32.4%	14503	59296
HABE	9,900	9,782	-118	-1.2%	18,118	8,218	83.0%	40.9%	4050	13950
GOCR	4,852	4,902	50	1.0%	9,092	4,240	87.4%	44.2%	2145	6997
GRMO	2,120	2,165	45	2.1%	2,978	858	40.5%	21.3%	452	2572
CHRO	12,121	12,398	277	2.3%	13,328	1,207	10.0%	6.1%	742	12863
LAWA	10,149	10,736	587	5.8%	20,734	10,585	104.3%	55.0%	5586	15735
PETT	2,647	2,802	155	5.9%	4,891	2,244	84.8%	45.3%	1200	3847

5. IMPLICATIONS FOR MANAGEMENT AND POLICY

Regression analysis can be used to identify parks with high R-squared values, indicating that there is an observed relationship that can potentially be utilized to refine visitation estimates, and parks with low R-squared values, indicating a discrepancy between the datasets and likely an underlying visitor behavior that is unaccounted for in one or both datasets.

Both VPVM-VE and MTD are estimates that have limitations or sources of error. VPVM-VE can be influenced by multipliers, inaccurate vehicle counts, or the inclusion of non-visitor vehicles, while MTD may miss visitors without mobile devices, suffer from limited cell coverage, or fail to capture short visits. Understanding the strengths and uncertainties inherent in these data is crucial when interpreting their relationship.

For parks with high R-squared values, utilizing a hybrid formula that combines Visitors Per Vehicle Multiplier - Visitation Estimates (VPVM-VE) and Mobile Tracking Data (MTD) offers significant benefits for park management. This hybrid approach leverages the strengths of both data sources, as indicated by their high correlation. By combining these two sources, a hybrid formula can help mitigate the weaknesses of each. Three methods for utilizing both datasets for parks that are highly correlated can be considered:

- **Method 1:** If only VPVM-VE is available in the future, the HVE leverages the snapshot of the relationship from 2022 to modify the estimates.
- **Method 2:** If MTD is regularly acquired, it could be used to replace VPVM-VE. This method adjusts raw MTD using the observed relationship to produce an HVE.
- **Method 3:** MTD and VPVM-VE are obtained monthly and a weighted combination of both is used in the HVE.

As Method 1 uses the least resources, as it requires no additional MTD, it could work to improve estimates. However, if a shift in visitor dynamics happens, it would be missed and the HVE could amplify an issue in the VPVM-VE. Both methods 2 and 3 require the purchase of MTD; however, method 2 could be a good option if park equipment needs to be removed due to malfunction or relocation.

All of these HVE methods could enable park managers to make more informed, data-driven decisions regarding resource allocation, infrastructure development, and targeted marketing strategies, ultimately enhancing visitor experiences, promoting equitable access, and supporting sustainability across the park system.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

For Parks with Low R-Squared Values:

Investigating the Vehicle Multiplier: Perform a regression analysis comparing raw vehicle counts (without multipliers) and MTD to identify whether the vehicle multiplier is distorting data or if MTD is missing significant visitation. This will highlight data issues and help improve visitation estimates. Alternatively, if new mobile data could be acquired, regression analysis using vehicle count data collected for this project (no multiplier) and 2024 mobile data for any low-r-squared parks that had vehicle count data collected to see if there is no relationship for a different year and without the multipliers.

Improving Data Collection: If no significant relationship is found, alternative data collection methods or a reevaluation of how visitation is measured may be required. Further research should focus on identifying non-vehicle access points, such as walking paths, and addressing MTD limitations, such as poor cell coverage, visitors without mobile devices, or incomplete vehicle counts. Additionally, monitoring shifts in visitor behavior and seasonal trends may reveal new factors influencing visitation data.

For Parks with High R-Squared Values:

Without Immediate Additional MTD Investment: Create a park-specific Hybrid Visitation Estimate (HVE) by adjusting VPVM-VE with the park's specific regression statistics for slope and intercept. High slopes (above 1) should be reduced, and low slopes (below 1) should be increased to align with a 1:1 relationship that represents a perfect correlation, where the number of vehicle visits matches the number of mobile visits exactly. If the intercept is high, it may suggest overestimation by VPVM-VE, requiring adjustments to better align estimates with actual visitor behavior, especially where mobile data is underrepresented.

Future Additional MTD Investment: Changing visitor dynamics, such as shifts in demographics or visitation patterns may render the HVE less accurate over time. Verifying that data relationships are similar four to five years from now could identify any of these issues and provide updated HVE formulas that capture a more current year's relationship.

With Immediate Additional MTD Investment: When resources allow, incorporating both datasets regularly is recommended. This approach fills gaps left by one dataset with data from the other, offering a more comprehensive understanding of park usage.

APPENDIX A. Regression Analysis Result Plots (Panels A-E)

The panels below present regression plots for each park, illustrating the relationship between VPVM-VE in thousands on the y-axis and MTD in thousands on the x-axis. Each plot provides a detailed view of the correlation between the two datasets, indicated by R-squared values, slopes, and intercepts. The diagonal 1:1 line represents a perfect correlation, where the number of vehicle visits matches the number of mobile visits exactly. Each data point corresponds to specific months in 2022, with color coding to differentiate between the months. The colors of the plots correspond to the regions of the parks: blue represents coastal parks, magenta indicates Piedmont parks, and green is used for mountain parks.

Panel A: Coastal

Panel B - Coastal & Piedmont

Panel C - Piedmont

Panel D - Piedmont & Mountains

Panel E - Mountains

- 1:1
- Jan
- Feb
- ▲ Mar
- ▲ Apr
- ▲ May
- ◆ Jun
- ◆ Jul
- ◆ Aug
- Sep
- Oct
- Nov
- Dec